

Precision Gait Analysis and Event Detection Using IMUs: A Comparative Evaluation with Insole Pressure Readings

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Abstract—Neurological disorders, such as Parkinson’s, multiple sclerosis, and stroke, are a major global disability and mortality cause. Balance impairments can lead to falls, emotional distress, and reduced autonomy. To address these issues, tailored interventions through rehabilitation techniques, assistive technologies, and therapeutic exercises are essential. The TeleRehaB Decision Support System (DSS) is a clinical and cost-effective tool designed to enhance telerehabilitation for patients with balance disorders. The system uses artificial intelligence (AI) with wearable and IoT devices for remote monitoring and management. The DSS evaluates prognostic factors, therapeutic efficacy, patient outcomes, and potential adverse effects, and customizes rehabilitation plans based on factors like disorder type, intervention intensity, technology utilization, and patient compliance. The study uses Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) and pressure-sensing insoles for gait dynamics analysis in patients with neurological deficits, aiming to refine gait event detection and provide a comprehensive view of patient mobility. This study conducted gait cycle experiments using Insole Pressure Units (IMUs) in a laboratory setting, demonstrating their high precision in capturing dynamic gait events. The results showed strong positive correlations, especially in two-way tasks, indicating advanced predictive capabilities.

Index Terms—balance disorders, telerehabilitation, gait analysis, virtual physiotherapist

I. INTRODUCTION

Motor deficits have an effect on activities of daily living, with locomotion and balance being essential for indepen-

dence [1]. Individuals grappling with balance disorders face multifaceted challenges that significantly impact their daily lives. Balance disorders disrupt body equilibrium, causing dizziness, vertigo, and instability [2]. They compromise physical capabilities, emotional distress, and independence. Older adults are disproportionately affected, with falls leading to injuries and decreased mobility [3]. Management requires a comprehensive approach considering physiological systems and tailored interventions [4], [5].

Our approach involves integrating AI in balance rehabilitation by merging wearables and IoT devices for remote patient monitoring management. The system utilizes retrospective data to evaluate prognostic factors, treatment effectiveness, outcomes, and side effects. It tailors rehabilitation interventions by considering factors such as type, intensity, technology usage, and projected compliance, serving patients with diverse risk profiles. Our system enables automated remote monitoring, facilitating real-time performance assessment while virtual physiotherapists provide timely feedback. Through these integrated methods, we establish a closed-loop coaching system that fosters personalized, data-driven interventions [6].

In this study, we use Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) and pressure-sensing insoles to analyze gait dynamics in patients with neurological conditions. By leveraging machine learning algorithms and comprehensive data analytics, we aim to validate the accuracy of these techniques against traditional methods. This research represents a significant step in en-

hancing rehabilitation strategies through advanced technology, offering a detailed insight into the movement patterns and balance issues of patients with stroke, MCI, and long-term COVID-19. This novel approach not only aims to enhance the precision of gait event detection but also seeks to offer a holistic view of patient mobility, aiding in the development of more effective rehabilitation techniques tailored to individual needs.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development of TeleRehaB DSS is determined by the overall needs of patients with stroke, MCI and long Covid-19 in patient’s health and quality of life.

The main components of system are used in our study are depicted in Fig. 1. Key system components include a web-based backend for remote exercise prescription and monitoring (Physiotherapist Portal), a user-friendly patient platform for home exercises, smart glasses for the implementation of AR and VR rehabilitation training activities at home, IMUs, and a depth camera for exercise tracking and feedback. Additionally, the system integrates reporting tools for physiotherapists to monitor compliance and progress, even in remote settings.

A. System Architecture

In our data acquisition process, we utilize four Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors strategically placed on the ankles, back, and head, alongside an RGB camera capturing the skeletal points of the patient. To ensure seamless data collection, users are advised to maintain a distance of no more than 2 meters from the edge computer and a consistent 4 meters from the camera throughout the exercise.

Before platform initiation, users input the MAC addresses of the IMU sensors and Bluetooth dongle addresses into the configuration file. Subsequently, the system prompts users for essential information, including Patient ID, Session ID, and Group. Upon selecting ‘connect IMU sensors,’ the application provides real-time updates on sensor connectivity. Once all IMU sensors are successfully connected, the camera interface activates. Users can then initiate the exercise with the ‘start recording’ option. Post-exercise, users conclude by selecting ‘stop recording.’ All recorded data is systematically saved with the respective recording date, while the log file adopts a nomenclature based on the Patient ID, Session ID, and entered Group Fig. 2 .

B. Virtual Physiotherapist

Holographic displays and AR integration in healthcare offer immersive experiences, allowing medical professionals to interact with patient data and virtual models. Body-worn sensors capture patient data, enabling precise evaluation of performance and progression. The system’s backend processes real-time data from sensors using machine learning algorithms to interpret and analyze this information. This helps in customizing exercise regimens, adjusting difficulty levels, and identifying potential issues. The holographic interface provides an intuitive platform for patients to engage with

Fig. 1. Experimental setup for a physiotherapy session using TeleRehaB DSS system. The camera is positioned on the right/left of the computer, according to the limb (right / left) that is being rehabilitated.

Fig. 2. TeleRehaB DSS Application and Dashboard.

exercises, with the AR avatar or holographic representation of a physiotherapist guiding them. The system’s software manages patient data, treatment plans, exercise progressions, and communication between healthcare providers and patients. The technical infrastructure aims to enhance patient engagement, improve treatment outcomes, and provide healthcare professionals with valuable insights for informed decision-making and personalized care delivery.

C. Gait Metrics and Analytics

The system uses Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors to detect gait events, calculate joint angles, and validate them. It uses Euler angle differential calculations, spatial parameter computation, and joint angle estimation. Validation and reliability are ensured through comparative experiments with a camera-based system. Threshold-based methods focus on temporal relationships, while machine learning algorithms use labeled data and IMU-derived features. Hidden Markov Models capture temporal dynamics and pattern recognition extracts characteristic patterns. The system provides a comprehensive dataset for AI-based prognostic models related to balance disorders.

The gait analysis experiment was conducted in a laboratory setting with no human participants involved. The primary objective was to assess the precision and accuracy of inertial measurement units (IMUs) in capturing gait dynamics through various walking tasks. The IMUs used were capable of measuring angular velocities and accelerations in three-dimensional space. The experiment was divided into two main tasks: Task One (OneWay) consisted of a straightforward 10-step walking motion, while Task Two (TwoWay) involved a complex movement pattern with a 5-step rotation followed by a 5-step linear motion. Each task was replicated multiple times

to validate the consistency of the data. Data was collected at a high sampling rate to ensure detailed capture of the gait cycle. The raw data was then processed using a combination of filtering algorithms to isolate relevant gait events such as heel strikes and toe-offs.

Fig. 3. Event Detection in Gait Analysis: Heel Strikes and Toe-Offs over Time.

This diagram illustrates the precise moments of heel strikes and toe-offs during the gait cycle. Each peak corresponds to a heel strike, and each trough indicates a toe-off. The clear demarcation of these events validates the IMUs' sensitivity to distinct phases of the walking motion Fig. 3.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Gait Analysis

In the investigation of gait cycles using IMUs, correlation analyses for both one-way and two-way tasks revealed strong relationships between recorded extremum values and specific gait events. For the one-way task, the left leg showed very strong positive correlations, with coefficients ranging from 0.926 for Toe and Min to 0.967 for Toe and Max, while the right leg exhibited even higher correlations, between 0.972 for Heel and Min and 0.991 for Toe and Max, indicating a near-perfect predictive capability of the IMUs for gait event detection. Contrastingly, the two-way task presented almost perfect correlations for the left leg, with coefficients above 0.997 for all events, and slightly lower yet still significant correlations for the right leg, hovering around 0.997 to 0.999. These findings highlight the precision of IMUs in tracking heel strikes and toe-offs, with the two-way task demonstrating marginally superior correlation, possibly due to the increased complexity of movement.

These sets of diagrams (Left Insole - angX, angY, angZ; Right Insole - angX, angY, angZ) represent the angular motion recorded by the IMUs in the X, Y, and Z axes over time. The repeated patterns reflect the consistency of the walking tasks, and the mirroring between the left and right insoles indicates symmetrical motion akin to bipedal locomotion Fig. 4 Fig. 5.

From the scatter plots is presented a variation in extremal values for heel and toe data points throughout the gait cycle.

Fig. 4. OneWay: IMU-Based Insole Angular Data Analysis Over 10 Steps.

Fig. 5. TwoWay: IMU-Insole Angular Data Over 10 Steps with Mid-Walk Rotation Analysis.

In bidirectional leg diagrams, data points show a dispersion, indicating variability between rotational and linear ambulatory tasks Fig. 7. In unidirectional leg diagrams, uniformity is observed, indicating consistency in single-mode walking tasks Fig. 6. This pattern may suggest a correlation between gait variability and task complexity, requiring further investigation.

B. Gait Evaluation

The study evaluated event detection accuracy by comparing IMU data and pressure readings from insoles. Two distinct data collection methods were used, with the first involving ten repetitions of ten steps and the second involving ten repetitions of five steps followed by a rotation. The comparison was made by recording time events from insoles and identifying min-max

Fig. 6. Oneway Gait Correlation.

Fig. 7. TwoWay Gait Correlation.

peaks in IMU data. The aim was to validate event detection accuracy by utilizing the complementary aspects of IMUs capturing motion dynamics and insoles providing insights into pressure distribution or related foot movement parameters. The comparative analysis helped understand the congruence and divergence between the two systems Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Correlation of IMU-Derived Acceleration and Pressure Data in Simulated Left Leg Gait Cycle. This graph showcases the filtered acceleration data along the y-axis for both simulated left and right legs. The waveform patterns correlate to the rhythmic acceleration and deceleration expected in a bipedal gait cycle.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our study explores the use of Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) and advanced technology to enhance balance physiotherapy exercises. The TeleRehab Decision Support System (DSS) is demonstrated as a cost-effective and home-based solution for improving balance rehabilitation. The DSS uses AI-driven prognostic models and real-time monitoring to tailor

interventions to individual patient needs, promoting independence and quality of life for those with balance impairments. The precision of IMUs in capturing gait events is highlighted, and the system's reliability is validated through IMU data and insole pressure readings. This study underscores the importance of personalized and data-driven interventions in balance rehabilitation. Further research and clinical implementation of such systems hold the potential to significantly impact the management of balance impairments on a broader scale.

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